
Emerging Challenges In Social Sciences And Humanities In India

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15266441

Abstract:

In modern scientific era there are number of problems in society. India is not an exception for that. There were problems in India but the nature of problems was different. We didn't have enough food; we can not control diseases. After scientific revolution we have remedies over these problems but we have invited some problems. One should have taken care of unwanted effects/demerits of scientific revolutions. And here, is the role of Social sciences. We should have balance between development of science and social science. In India, we forgot social science while focusing on scientific development. We have not given enough importance to social science in the development of nation. The attitude towards social science is negative in general. Students who are studying science are assumed to be prestigious in our society whereas studying in social sciences feels inferior. We cannot think development of a nation without social science study. The researchers have studied these social problems and suggested some remedies in this paper.

Keywords - Social Science, Scientific Revolution, Development, Attitudes, Inferior, Remedies.

Introduction:

Social Sciences are very important because they help to develop a matured person to understand his role in society, to build a nation. Social Sciences is the parts of learning and study which recognise the simultaneous and mutual action of physical and no-physical stimuli which produce social reaction. Social Sciences enable us (students of Social Science) to give sense of belonging to a place, to a community, to a nation and to the world. In short, social science is a study of human relationship. Social Sciences help us to solve the problems of individual and social level. In modern time of globalization there are number of Social problems in society. There are number of issues related to social sciences like, unemployment, increasing number of suicides in every field, female foeticide, social clashes, continuously rising prices, migration of people for jobs, riot, decreasing ethical values in society, dowry

customs, superstitions, life threatening diseases, and so on.¹ Natural calamities-droughts, earthquake, floods-like in Kerala, are adding extra burden to it. Looking towards the history of India, we can realise that there were problems in India but the nature of problems was different. We didn't have enough food; we can not control diseases like Plague, small pox. After scientific revolution we have remedies over these problems but we have invited some problems. One should have taken care of unwanted effects/demerits of scientific revolutions. We should have balance between development of science and social science. In India, we forgot social science while focusing on scientific development. Our research in social science is negligible. We have not given enough importance to social science in the development of nation. The attitude towards social science is negative in general. Students who are studying science are assumed to be

prestigious in our society whereas those studying in social science feel inferior.

Social sciences have following challenges:

- 1) Revolution of science and technology is kind of challenge to Social Science
- 2) Lack of support system and limited resources available to Social Science in society.
- 3) Lack of job opportunities and limited scope to Social Science than science and technology. 4) Lack of research aptitude in Social Science than in science and technology.
- 4) Lack of Awareness of importance of Social Science in development of a nation.
- 5) Studying Social Science is not well recognised in developing nation like India.
- 6) Developing skill oriented courses for the students of Social Sciences.

Discussion:

Revolution of science and technology is kind of challenge to Social Science: After the revolution of science and technology, bright students seek admission in the field and the social branch of social science neglected. Academically poor students are admitted in the faculty of social sciences. So this branch has such type of student class, who takes learning very casually. Some institutions educational loans to career oriented courses but they are not providing to social science courses, because they do not have guarantee of jobs in social science.² Social Sciences have less job opportunities and limited scope than science and technology. Research is the most important activity for development of the any subject. Hence, research in Social Science in also important. But it is neglected in some way in India. The importance of research is not addressed properly in society. The research aptitude is not developed in society. People are not cooperative in research activity. Many times they give fake

answers or social answers to the questionnaire of researcher. So it leads to wrong conclusion. It is very hazardous to society. As a result, the funding agencies are also becomes reluctant to provide funds to such research. So doing research in Social Science is a Challenge for researcher in India. There are a few funding agencies in India who provide funds to Social Science Research. So funding is also a big challenge, rather doing research in low fund (budget) Social Science is also a challenge for a researcher.³ According to the committee, in the pre-independence period, the scale and scope of both these was quite limited: universities and other academic institutions, the main canthers of scholarly research at that time, were relatively few. There requirements of information and analyses for government were also quite limited. The post British -Independent India witnessed a vastly expanded role for government in engineering economic development and social changes. It also saw the rapid growth of modern industrial and commercial enterprises. Political controversies and public interest in issues relating to public policy and their social implications generated an economy and society.

Several new universities with departments for teaching and research in different social science disciplines were established. The Planning Commission initially played a leading role in (a) involving social scientists (mostly economists) from the university system in preparing development plans, monitoring their implementation and impact; and (b) encouraging and supporting research done by scholars in universities through a large number of projects on diverse subjects. Government departments began to show increasing interest in establishing or expanding specialized institutes under their control. They also started sponsoring research projects in universities and study units in existing universities and institutions

to conduct research on specified subjects. The number of university departments and research institutions in the field of social sciences has since grown manifold. Besides funding the creation and expansion of social science faculties in universities and colleges, the University Grants Commission, New Delhi has initiated a programme to fund Centres of Advanced Studies in university departments with outstanding faculty, and Special Assistance Programmes to nurture and support promising university departments in different social sciences to expand their research capabilities. The funding for fellowships for doctoral and post-doctoral research was increased.¹³ Government departments and public sector organizations and, more recently, UN agencies, aid agencies of foreign governments, international financial agencies, and private foundations have also shown increasing interest in funding research on socio-economic human behaviour and societal change, knowledge and learning, economic benefits, health and welfare aspects associated with biological diversity. Furthermore, for assessing research on the management of biodiversity, it is vital to involve scholars with knowledge on societal strategies for conservation and sustainable use, legal, economic and communicative instruments, physical planning, actors and various forms of collaboration. This calls for a diversity of social science and humanities disciplines. If we try to sensitize people in this regard and proved importance of Social Research to society, it will be helpful. There are so many reasons for absentee, lack of motivation, unemployment; some of them have to earn their livelihood while learning. Social Sciences help us to develop an insight into human relationship, social values, and attitudes and also help us appreciate other culture, along with our rich cultural heritage.⁴

Thus Social Sciences play crucial role in developing nation. But students are not interested in studying Social Science so far. So it is a challenge. Studying Social Science is not prestigious in our country. As bright students are seeking admission to Science and technology, these branches are automatically becoming prestigious.¹² The students are getting jobs in science and technology immediate after completing education. But in Social Science the situation is different. Students are not employed in that proportion. So the motivation of the students of Social Science is affected. Developing skill oriented courses for the students of Social Sciences. There are a few skill oriented courses in Social sciences because Social science fosters overall development of a student. It creates sole background for job.⁶ So creating further preparation of student is lengthy process. So developing skill oriented courses along with basic / fundamental developmental courses is a challenge for Social Sciences.

Remedies:

- 1) The science and technology should work with the social sciences research. The interrelations can be established to study the social structure and the development of the society.⁷
- 2) Social science research should be encouraged with sufficient funds and utilities. The national policy should be decided on social structure.
- 3) Funds availability and the awareness in the social development project can provide job opportunities in the field. Change in curriculum with respects to the current scenario of the societies. E.g. IT field social problems⁸
- 4) Students involvement in basic problems and its effect on social issues can encourage the logical thinking in the students. The students can solve minor problems during study and develop interest in the social developments.⁹

- 5) Social development and the technology development are interrelated in developed nations. The developing nation society and the problems should be focused during the policy making. 6) The social science should be included in the developing policy of nation.¹⁰
- 6) Skill courses are the base building courses for the research in the social sciences. The skill courses can enhance the skills and capacity of the students for the research in India¹¹.

Conclusion:

Social Science plays an important role in development of a nation. The life of a nation is depends on the development of research attitude in social sciences. Social sciences help a nation to develop. So the role of Social Sciences is very crucial in the development of a nation. Social Scientists had made history in the western world. Social Scientist created awareness in society about the life values, like Independence, Democracy, Nationality, self-dignity, Humanity, etc. In the context of the social crisis and constant transformation of social network in globalization are the major challenges to Social studies. The challenges are fundamentally social and human in nature. They are the result of individual and collective human behaviour. So the social sciences and humanities must play a central role in understanding and tackling the problems. They help us deal with the change and since change is constant, the social sciences and humanities will always be an important part of the research. The social science and humanities are essential because they help us understand ourselves and why we do and what we do.

References:

1. Chatterjee Subhrajit (2015), Social Science Research in India: Basic Challenges International Research Journal of Interdisciplinary & Multidisciplinary Studies (IRJIMS)

- Volume-I, Issue-VII, August 2015, Page No. 50-55 Published by: Scholar Publications, Karimganj, Assam, India, 788711 Website: <http://www.irjims.com>
2. Abdulhameed, Abdulhameed, E.,(n.d) Raising Submissive and Dependent Citizens: the Case of Egyptian Schools.
 3. Browne, 2013 Civic education: approaches and efficacy GSDRC helpdesk research report (2013)
 4. Huutoniemi K, Klein JK, Bruun H and Hukkinen J (2010) Analyzing interdisciplinarity: Typology and indicators. *Research Policy*; 39 (1): 79–88
 5. Klein JT(2008) Education. In: Hirsch Hadorn G, (eds). *Handbook of Transdisciplinary Research*, Springer: Dordrecht, The Netherlands, pp 399–401.
 6. Frodeman R (2011) Interdisciplinary research and academic sustainability: Managing knowledge in an age of accountability. *Environmental Conservation*; 38 (2): 105–112
 7. Wagner CS et al. (2011) Approaches to understanding and measuring interdisciplinary scientific research. *Journal of Informatics*; 5 (1): 14–26
 8. Langfeldt L, Godø H, Gornitzka A and Kaloudis A (2012) Integration modes in EU research: Centrifugalise versus coordination of national research policies. *Science and Public Policy*; 39 (1): 88–98
 9. Ahmed, N.M., 2000. “The Impact of Globalization the Institutionalization of Social Crisis” Posted: January, 11, 2002. WWW.mediamonitors.net/mosaddeq28.html
 10. Chase-Dunn, C and Rubinson, R.T., 1977. “Toward a structural Perspective on the World System”. *Politics and Society*, 7, 453-476
 11. Sivarajan K., Thulasidharam T.V., Vijayan N.K.(2007) “Social Science Education”, Calicut University, Calicut.
 12. Vaidyanathan, A. “Social Science Research in India: Some Emerging Issues.” *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 36, no. 2, 2001, pp. 112–114. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/4410165.